

Spatial Planning: A prerequisite for Sustainable Development of Bangladesh

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Abstract

Among nations with populations above 100 million, Bangladesh is the most densely populated. It is located on the most active delta in the world and quite vulnerable to natural calamities. Despite tremendous growth over the last three decades in the service, industrial and remittance sector, agriculture remains the largest single source of the GDP and employment. It also provides the nation with food security, a crucial component of sustainability. Over the last three decades unplanned urbanization and industrialization has adversely affected ecologically critical areas such as wetlands, rivers and forests and ecosystems. Natural hydrology has been affected by increased extraction of groundwater and surface water for irrigation, coupled with flood control measures in the upper riparian and lower riparian regions. In this context, spatial planning could be considered as a useful tool to foster sustainable development of the country. Therefore, this paper recommends spatial planning as a tool for sustainable development for Bangladesh considering the demographic trends, economy, geographic context and review of existing related policy of land use and urban planning.

1 Introduction

According to the World Bank (2015b), Bangladesh has emerged from a lower income nation to embark on the path to become a middle income nation within coming decade. Compared to its neighbors its performance has been noteworthy in many sectors. However, the demographic patterns, geographic context and economic trends all point towards unprecedented complexities arising from various issues such as overcrowding in urban settlements, unplanned urbanization, climate change, water resources management issues, shrinking farmland, infrastructure deficit etc. (World Bank, 2014). The prevailing practice of land use and urban management and weak governance further exacerbate the situation. In such a scenario, this paper highlights the demographic, economic and geographic context of Bangladesh and advocates the necessity of spatial planning on a nationwide basis to ensure its sustainable development.

2 A brief overview of the demographic trends of Bangladesh

Bangladesh is one of the most densely populated territories in the world, particularly in which there exist a high dependence on agricultural sector, as we can see in Table 1 and 2. The territories which have higher or similar density are essentially city states with much lower aggregate population. The land area excluding the water bodies, rivers, lakes is 130,170 sq-km. At present, in 2015, the population is estimated to be 160 million making a density of 1200 persons per sq-km or 5 persons per acre and in 2050, population is projected to be 200 million that will make a density of 1500 persons per sq-km or 6.25 persons per acre, as seen in Figure 1 (UN, 2015).

UN (2015) predicts that the population will taper off at around 200 million, but Streatfield and Karar (2008) provide an explanation of population distribution which reveals that the rural population will stop growing by 2025 while the urban population will absorb the additional growth.

Table 1: Population statistics of major nations of the world

		Country Name	Population	Area (Sq. Km.)	Population Density (Sq. Km.)	Area (Sq. Mi.)	Population Density (Sq. Mi.)
1		China	1,339,190,000	9,596,960.00	139.54	3,705,405.45	361.42
2		India	1,184,639,000	3,287,590.00	360.34	1,269,345.07	933.27
3		United States of America	309,975,000	9,629,091.00	32.19	3,717,811.29	83.38
4		Indonesia	234,181,400	1,919,440.00	122.01	741,099.62	315.99
5		Brazil	193,364,000	8,511,965.00	22.72	3,286,486.71	58.84
6		Pakistan	170,260,000	803,940.00	211.78	310,402.84	548.51
7		Nigeria	170,123,000	923,768.00	171.32	356,668.67	443.71
8		Bangladesh	164,425,000	144,000.00	1,141.84	55,598.69	2,957.35
9		Russia	141,927,297	17,075,200.00	8.31	6,592,768.87	21.53
10		Japan	127,380,000	377,835.00	337.13	145,882.85	873.17
11		Mexico	108,396,211	1,972,550.00	54.95	761,605.50	142.33
12		Philippines	94,013,200	300,000.00	313.38	115,830.60	811.64
13		Vietnam	85,789,573	329,560.00	260.32	127,243.78	674.21
14		Germany	81,757,600	357,021.00	229.00	137,846.52	593.11
15		Ethiopia	79,221,000	1,127,127.00	70.29	435,185.99	182.04
16		Egypt	78,848,000	1,001,450.00	78.73	386,661.85	203.92
17		Iran	75,078,000	1,648,000.00	45.56	636,296.10	117.99
18		Turkey	72,561,312	780,580.00	92.96	301,383.50	240.76
19		Congo (Dem. Rep. of)	67,827,000	2,345,410.00	28.92	905,567.49	74.90
20		France	65,447,374	547,030.00	119.64	211,209.38	309.87

Source: (World Bank, 2015a).

Table 2. Population Densities of countries and territories.

Netherlands	493	495	497	498	
Korea, Rep.	508	512	514	516	
San Marino	514	517	521	524	
St. Martin (French part)	556	563	569	575	
Aruba	564	566	569	572	
Mauritius	616	617	619	620	
West Bank and Gaza	633	652	672	693	
Barbados	652	655	659	662	
Maldives	1,086	1,107	1,128	1,150	
Sint Maarten (Dutch part)	1,113	1,132	1,150	1,167	
Bangladesh	1,161	1,174	1,188	1,203	
Malta	1,295	1,301	1,311	1,323	
Bermuda	1,302	1,291	1,296	1,300	
Bahrain	1,647	1,701	1,734	1,753	
Hong Kong SAR, China	6,690	6,735	6,814	6,845	
Singapore	7,252	7,405	7,589	7,713	
Macao SAR, China	18,001	18,270	18,622	18,942	
Monaco	18,423	18,631	18,790	18,916	
South Sudan					

1980-1984 1985-1989 1990-1994 1995-1999 2000-2004 2005-2009 2010-2014

Source: (World Bank, 2015a).

Table 3: The population density of the districts of Bangladesh.

Statistical Region	2001 Population (in thousand)	Area (sq.km)	Population Density (per sq.km)	Area (sq.mile)	Population Density (per sq.mile)
Dhaka	18,404	7,439	2,474	2,880	6,390
Mymensingh	9,401	9,862	953	3,808	2,469
Jamalpur	3,531	3,394	1,040	1,310	2,695
Faridpur	6,336	7,008	904	2,669	2,374
Tangail	3,413	3,414	1,000	1,309	2,607
Chittagong	8,780	7,775	1,129	2,786	3,151
Cgt. Hill Tract	1,403	13,295	106	5,089	276
Noakhali	5,505	5,985	920	2,033	2,708
Comilla	9,635	6,716	1,435	2,592	3,717
Sylhet	8,262	12,596	656	4,783	1,777
Rajshahi	7,971	9,441	844	3,653	2,182
Dinajpur	4,909	6,652	738	2,609	1,882
Rangpur	9,506	9,666	983	3,701	2,568
Bogra	4,051	3,885	1,043	1,501	2,699
Pabna	5,063	4,869	1,040	1,906	2,656
Khulna	6,020	12,212	493	4,631	1,300
Barisal	6,114	8,260	740	2,792	2,190
Patuakhali	2,416	5,037	480	1,675	1,442
Jessore	5,814	6,567	885	2,584	2,250
Kushtia	3,483	3,495	997	1,342	2,595

Source: (Rashid, 2005, BBS, 2005) Page 42.

Table 4: Trend of Structural Transformation of Broad Sectoral Shares in GDP and Growth Rate at Constant Price.

Share (in percent)										
Sector	1980-81	1985-86	1990-91	1995-96	2000-01	2005-06	2010-11	2011-12	2012-13	2013-14*
Agriculture	33.07	31.15	29.23	25.68	25.03	19.01	18.01	17.38	16.78	16.33
Industry	17.31	19.13	21.04	24.87	26.20	25.40	27.38	28.08	29.00	29.61
Service	49.62	49.73	49.73	49.45	48.77	55.59	54.61	54.54	54.22	54.05
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
Average growth rate (in percent)										
Agriculture	3.31	3.31	2.23	3.10	3.14	5.50	4.46	3.01	2.46	3.35
Industry	5.13	6.72	4.57	6.98	7.45	9.80	9.02	9.44	9.64	8.39
Service	3.55	4.10	3.28	3.96	5.53	6.60	6.22	6.58	5.51	5.83
GDP (At producer prices)	3.74	3.34	3.24	4.47	5.41	7.18	6.64	6.72	6.14	6.16

Source: (BBS, 1993, BBS, 2006)

Table 5: Growth of Urban Population in Bangladesh 1901-2001

Census year	Total national population (million)	Annual growth rate of national population (%)	Total urban population (million)	Urban population as % of total population (level of urbanization)	Decadal increase of urban population (%)	Annual (exponential) growth rate of urban population, (%)
1901	28.2	—	0.70	2.43	—	—
1911	31.65	0.94	0.80	2.54	14.96	1.39
1922	33.25	0.60	0.87	2.61	8.85	0.84
1931	35.60	0.74	1.07	3.01	22.20	2.00
1941	41.99	1.70	1.54	3.66	43.20	3.59
1951	44.17	0.50	1.83	4.34	18.38	1.58
1961	55.22	2.26	2.64	5.19	45.11	3.72
1974	76.37	2.48	6.00	8.87	137.57	6.62
1981	89.91	2.32	13.56	15.54	110.68	10.03
1991	111.45	2.17	22.45	20.15	69.75	5.43
2001	123.1	1.47	28.61	23.10	37.05	3.25

Source: (BBS, 1993, BBS, 2005, BBS, 2006)

Therefore, along with this mammoth population density issue, the distribution of the population over the country is also very significant. The primacy of the capital city Dhaka and its adjacent urban agglomerations is shown in Table 3.

While development of human resources has been given due importance in the sectoral policies, little attention has been given on how to manage such an overwhelming population spatially in this tiny land mass. Many economists have recognized scarcity of land as the key hurdle for economic development (Rashid, 2013).

3 Trends of Economic Growth of Bangladesh and the Urbanization Scenario

In post liberation decades, the economy of Bangladesh was primarily based on agriculture and at the same time heavily dependent on the support from the development partners. Since 1990s, the economic trend has been shifted with a clear inclination towards non-agricultural sector. This shift is mainly fueled by the growth of various non-agricultural sectors such as of the export oriented ready-made garments (RMG) industry, service sector, remittance from the expatriate Bangladeshis etc. beside improved agricultural systems (Lewis, 2011). The distribution of different economic sectors and broad shares in GDP since the 80's are shown in Table 4. All these factors have accelerated the rate of urbanization, directly and indirectly, in various ways since the 1990s.

Urbanization of Bangladesh is heavily directed by factors such as distress migration, limited employment opportunities in the rural areas and growth of the new urban economy since the 1990's. According to the 2011 census, at present the total urban population of Bangladesh is estimated to be roughly 28% of the total population of 150.4 million. Although it has been predicted that the rate of urban population growth will fall over the coming years, it is projected by the UN that the urban population will be 86.5 million in 2030, that

will cross the 50% mark by 2040 and become 60% in 2050 to 100 million (Islam, 2012). The contribution of agriculture to the GDP is 15.1% and it employs 47% of the labor force (CIA, 2015) though the Government of Bangladesh projects the contribution to 16.33% (FDB-GOB, 2014). Food security plays a key role in the stability of this populous lower middle income nation.

Dhaka and Chittagong are the key centers of economic activity with existing population of 14 million and 4 million respectively. The contribution to the GDP of the urban areas is 45%. Islam (2012) has show that, with the massive improvement of road network over the last two decades, urbanization has followed clustered patterns with smaller urban settlements growing in tandem surrounding the larger cities, as depicted in Map 1. Large scale development of the road network and poor land-use administration and planning have resulted in almost endless sprawl along the key arterial highways, as seen in Figure 2, over the last decades. Sprawl has an adverse impact on the vulnerable natural hydrology and natural resources degradation.

4 The physical geography and environment of Bangladesh

Formed by the mighty Ganges and Brahmaputra river system, the Bengal Delta is the most dynamic on the

planet. The silt carried by the rivers form the major land masses and creates a plethora of variation with regard to soil characteristics, ecology, flooding patterns and consequently agro-ecology as described by Brammer (2012) and Rashid (2005). The key issues related to physiological features and correspondent natural phenomenon can be categorized into the following categories.

4.1 Hydrological Issues

Bangladesh has been classified into eight different zones based on its hydrological characteristics by Water Resources Planning Organization, GoB (WARPO). Zones for planning purposes are water stress zone, drought prone zone, four types of flood management zones and river channels used for navigation. The main threats to water security are as follows.

- a. Annual natural flooding, flash floods, impact of river control measures upstream and river erosion in upper riparian areas.
- b. Massive Sedimentation, Saline intrusion, tidal surge and storms associated with the Bay of Bengal in the coastal belt.
- c. Water management issues: Scarcity of water caused by unplanned use of underground aquifers for irrigation, potable water supply to urban areas, water pollution and unplanned diversion of water from rivers for agriculture and other uses. Some of these issues are shown in Maps 2, 3 and 4.

The National Water Policy, 1999 describes the main challenges of water resource management in the following way.

Water resources management in Bangladesh faces immense challenge for resolving many diverse problems and issues. The most critical of these are alternating flood and water scarcity during the wet and the dry seasons, ever-expanding water needs of a growing economy and population, and massive river sedimentation and bank erosion. There is a growing need for providing total water quality management (checking salinity, deterioration of surface water and groundwater quality, and water pollution), and maintenance of the eco-system. There is also an urgency to satisfy multi-sector water needs with limited resources, promote efficient and socially responsible water use, delineate public and private responsibilities, and decentralize state activities where appropriate. All of these have to be accomplished under severe constraints, such as the lack of control over rivers originating outside the country's borders, the difficulty of managing the deltaic plain, and the virtual absence of unsettled land for building water structures. (GOB, 1999)

4.2 Soil types, Bio-ecology and agro-ecology issues

Ali Reza et al. (2002) has divided the Bio Ecology of Bangladesh into 12 zones as shown in Map 6. The biodiversity of this relatively small land mass which includes rainforests, mangrove forests, protected forests, floodplains, wetlands and coastal zones with their ecotones, in terms of number and richness of floral and faunal species is critical for the ecological services required for the agro-ecology. The Food and Agricultural Organization classified 31 eco-agricultural zones. These vary widely in terms of agricultural productivity (Brammer, 2012).

5 Existing sectoral and spatial planning policies and implementing agencies of Bangladesh

5.1 Planning Agencies of Bangladesh

The National Planning Commission of Bangladesh functions as the apex body of the government for planning. The Prime Minister chairs the commission with the Minister of Planning as the Vice Chairman. Its key function to prepare, review, monitor and evaluate the national plans, both annual and five-year. The function also includes revising the perspective for the economic and social development of the country in accordance with the socio-economic objectives of the Government of Bangladesh. Its key departments are:

- i. Programming
- ii. General Economics
- iii. Socio-Economics
- iv. Physical Infrastructure
- v. Industry and Energy
- vi. Agriculture, Water & Rural Institutions

The planning division of the Ministry of planning plays the secretarial role to the key bodies for implementation of economic policies and projects known as the National Economic Council (NEC) and the Executive Committee of the National Economic Council (ECNEC).

The key function of the physical infrastructure division includes the preparation of short, medium, long-term plans for sectors under this Division, involving roads and highways, railway, civil aviation and tourism, post and telecommunication, statistics, water distribution, local and municipal infrastructure development, works and housing sectors (PCB-GOB, 2011). The National Planning Commission entrusts the concerned ministries with the task of implementing the policies.

5.2 Current Government Policies related to spatial planning:

5.2.1 Sectoral and spatial policies of the Sixth Five Year Plan FY2011-FY2015:

The current Sixth Five Year Plan contains the broad policy goals of the government. Bangladesh aims to become a middle income country by 2021 if the current rate of economic growth prevails. The government is

pursuing Vision 2021 to consolidate economic growth, improve service delivery, alleviate poverty, ensure environmental sustainability, manage human resource development, create planned urbanization, reduce regional disparity, address climate change adaption, enhance disaster resilience among other measures to ensure sustainable development (PCB-GOB, 2011).

Managing urbanization is given due emphasis. However, it does not address some key issues that are

critical in this regard. These issues can be viewed from three perspectives. The first one is the integration of sectoral policies with spatial strategies in both urban and rural context. The second one is the inadequacy of existing urban planning policies and implementation systems to cope with the massive scale of urbanization. The third issue is how to ensure integration of planning strategies of different government agencies involved in land management, water management, and infrastructure development, providing utility services, agriculture, environmental protection, climate change adaptation and disaster resilience.

There is a very clear bias in the Sixth Five Year Plan about now to use existing planning framework as well as legal instruments related to town-planning, area zoning and local government for developing urban centers. However, it does not provide any consideration to adopt a spatial planning strategy to accommodate the massive population, check environmental degradation and create resilience to climate change in the coming decades spanning the urban and rural areas on a national scale.

Agriculture is considered crucial for the sustenance of the country. Nevertheless, the decrease in arable land due to unplanned non-agrarian land use such as urbanization and industrialization is addressed by enhancing food production using modern technology. Taking steps to contain the footprint of settlements, spatial trends of urbanization and industrialization to protect arable land is not given due consideration.

The Sixth Five Year Plan also looks at population growth as an issue which has to be tackled with population control only. The population will stabilize by most estimates at 250 million. The cities and regions

need to be designed as such. The Draft National Urban Policy 2011 attempts to focus on building networks of urban centers but does not take into account the territorial issues which must be addressed to contain environmental issues.

5.2.2 National Land Use Policy 2001, Government of Bangladesh:

This document, prepared by the Ministry of Land, takes the key issues concerning depletion of agricultural land, misuse of land by various government and private agencies, land scarcity, unplanned urbanization, obsolete land management systems into cognizance and recommends for a national scale land zoning project. The local government will be responsible for preparing zoning maps. This project has produced digital land use maps for most of the parts of most of Bangladesh. The maps indicate basic land use but lacks the coordination with environment, infrastructure and urban planning.

5.2.3 Coastal Zone Policy (2005) Ministry of Water Resources. GoB:

This document takes the special needs of the coastal zones into careful consideration and layout the broad policy directions. The coastal zone has tremendous variations, with mangrove forests, estuarine ecological belts, delta zone, sea coast, agricultural land, non-agricultural land, shoals, embankment areas which have diverse requirements. Such a policy would only be effective if it had a spatial planning component with clear delegation of authority to a coastal land management authority which would monitor, plan, finance, evaluate and implement it.

Table 6: Key agencies involved in urban planning and infrastructure.

Agency	Parent Ministry	Key Responsibilities
Urban Development Directorate	Ministry of Housing and Public Works	Developing Master Plan/Land Use Plan for small, medium and large town and cities
Local Government and Engineering Department (LGED)	Ministry of Local Government, Rural Development and Cooperatives	Transportation, water supply and drainage and infrastructure planning and implementation, focusing on small urban centers outside the boundaries of Dhaka, Chittagong, Rajshahi, and Khulna.
National Housing Authority (NHA)	Ministry of Housing and Public Works	Addressing the housing needs of the country, particularly for the poor, the low and the middle-income group of people.
City Corporations of major cities	Ministry of Local Government, Rural Development and Cooperatives	Urban Management, Governance and planning
Rajdhani Unnayan Katripakkha (RAJUK), Chittagong Development Authority, Khulna Development Authority, Rajshahi Development Authority	Ministry of Housing and Public Works	Land use planning and transport planning. Implementation of land use planning of Dhaka, Chittagong, Rajshahi and Khulna.
Ministry of Communication	Ministry of Communication	Planning, design, construction and maintenance of road networks outside the city corporation boundaries

5.3 Policy framework related to physical planning

There is a huge policy gap between spatial and sectoral planning in Bangladesh. The spatial aspect of planning is seldom addressed when sectoral policies are framed. The Ministry of Planning is responsible for both sectoral planning and physical planning. The physical planning unit does not have the capacity to coordinate the planning activities undertaken by the various ministries involved. The prevailing spatial planning culture is essentially top down, based on very old euro-centric models and barely cognizant of environmental and socio-economic issues on a regional scale. There is little of effective legislative mechanism to control land-use changes in the rural areas. The major cities (Dhaka, Chittagong, Khulna, Rajshahi, Sylhet) are planned by government agencies such as Rajdhani Unnayan Karttripakkha (RAJUK) – Capital Development Authority for Dhaka, Chittagong Development Authority (CDA) for Chittagong etc. Such agencies have very little accountability to the public.

Such agencies primarily act as state-sponsored land development agencies to supply serviced land to the upper income group. Figure 4 shows an area of almost 9 square miles on a floodplain adjacent to the International Airport which was acquired by RAJUK and developed as serviced urban land. The entire drainage and ecosystem was destroyed. The elected local government agencies of the major City Corporations are barely involved in planning. There is an overlap of jurisdiction of urban planning and management between the key ministries involved, the Ministry of Housing and

Figure 4: Aerial views taken chronologically since 2005 from Google Earth showing how a vast floodplain and designated water retention pond and canals was acquired and filled by the government to supply serviced urban land over an area of approximately 9 square miles. This project is known as the Uttara 3rd Phase.

Source: Retrieved from Google Earth in June 2015

Figure 5: Aerial Map showing Hazaribagh Tannery area 2016. Red Areas show the Tanneries.

Source: Retrieved from Google Earth in August 2016

Public Works and the Ministry of Local Government namely as shown in Table 6. Extremely poor land management and governance issues further exacerbate the magnitude and impact of unplanned urbanization.

The impact of unplanned urbanization on the environment and the citizens can be epitomized by the Hazaribagh Tannery industries. Almost 200 industrial leather processing industries are located on 25 Ha on the banks of the river Buriganga in a densely populated neighborhood (Huq, 2000). This area has been named as the 5th most polluted place in the world by Zurich-based Green Cross Switzerland and New York-based Blacksmith Institute. Every day, the tanneries collectively dump 22,000 cubic liters of toxic waste, including cancer-causing hexavalent chromium, into the Buriganga, Dhaka's main river and a key water supply (Chandan, 2015). The industry developed on this area since the 1960's. Scant attention was paid to its extremely hazardous nature till the 1990's. The population of the surrounding residential areas grew rapidly and the Govt. ordered the industry to move to a new site located in Savar in 2003. In Savar, 200 acres of prime farmland was designated to become a "Leather City", with state of the art waste treatment facilities (Figure 6). Work has been in progress, yet a single factory has not shifted to that location till now. Bhowmik (2013) has stated that the choice of the relocation site at Savar on a fertile floodplain that is connected to the major rivers including the Buriganga is in direct violation of the Dhaka Structure Plan 1995-2015. The existence of Hazaribagh Tannery industry right in the middle of the city for almost six decades is an example of the failure of urban and environmental

planning and poor coordination between spatial and sectoral policy.

On the other hand, even in the face of extreme scarcity of serviced land, the Government mulls huge exclusive export processing zones, military installations, government institutions through acquiring huge amounts of agricultural land and even protected areas. Whereas proper use of underutilized public land is neglected (Nazem, 2013, Khan and Siddiqua, 2015, Rahman, 2008).

6 The impact of unplanned urbanization, inadequate physical planning systems and lack of regional planning strategies:

6.1 Impact of unplanned increase of non-agricultural land use and unsustainable practices in agriculture on land resources:

The direct impact of unplanned industrialization and urbanization has been the loss of agricultural land to non-farming uses. According to the Bangladesh Environment and Climate Change Outlook (ECCO) Report, it has been estimated that 1% of farmland is lost every year to non-farming uses. At this rate it is predicted that in 30 years, there will be no farmland (DOE-GOB, 2012).

The loss of agricultural land at such an alarming rate is threatening to the hard won food security gained over the last decades. Food security is an asset that forms the backbone of self-reliance.

Wetlands and forests are being rapidly converted to create settlements and industries which adversely affect ecosystem services. Over-farming, use of agro-chemicals and over utilization of land are leading to land degradation and reduction of soil productivity. Regarding this issue it is important to particularly mention about the adverse impact of unsustainable cultivation in the sloped terrain in Chittagong Hill Tracts, which is a tropical rainforest.

Unplanned infrastructural development is affecting natural terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems. This leads to degradation of indispensable natural services. Unplanned industrial development is causing pollution from industrial waste. Brick kilns, mining of riverbeds, shipbreaking etc. are causing irreversible damage to the land.

The ECCO report points out to the inadequacies in the policies. There is a gap in the spatial implications of the policies which makes them difficult to be implemented.

6.2 Impact of unplanned urbanization, industrialization, water, unsustainable practices in agriculture and other factors on water resources:

The demand for food production has propelled the over extraction of groundwater and surface water for irrigation. This has adversely impacted the fragile natural hydrological systems. Pollution from urban and industrial waste, filling up of lowlands, low floodplains and wetlands, upstream measures to control the flow of rivers using dams and intrusion of saline water from the estuarine system have further worsened the threats to water security. The temporal fluctuations of the water table and contamination of aquifers and pollution of surface water have led to the degradation of aquatic ecosystems, increase in waterborne diseases and scarcity of potable water. Reduced water flow in the Ganges, diverting rivers for irrigation and uncoordinated embankment systems have led to massive siltation of the river channels. Proper river basin management and water resources management is crucial for the ecosystem services they provide (DOE-GOB, 2012).

Figure 6:

- a. Site of new Leather Town at Savar, further upstream of the Buriganga adjacent to the river. Source Google Earth Images retrieved Aug.2016
- b. Aerial view showing the site in relationship with the city. Soon this area will also be within urban development.
- c. Site plan of the Leather city. The Effluent Treatment Plant is adjacent to the flood prone river. Source: Sheltech Consultants.
- d. Photograph showing proximity of Leather City with the river. The objectives of sustainable development.

Source: (6a) & (6b): Google Earth Images retrieved Aug.2016. (6c): Sheltech Consultants. (6d): Author

6.3 Impact of degradation of land and water resources and loss of habitat on biodiversity:

Agriculture, fishery, forestry are inter-related with the rich bio-diversity of Bangladesh. It boasts of about 5000

species of flora and 1600 species of fauna, a fact which proves the diversity of ecosystems in a relatively small geographic area. Degradation of land and water resources coupled with habitat loss has led to adverse conditions for the biodiversity to thrive (DOE-GOB, 2012).

6.4 Other impacts of unplanned urbanization and industrialization:

Industrial growth and lack of regional visions based on the growth of hierarchical networks of cities have led to urban sprawl as mentioned previously. Urban growth along the national arterial highways stretching outward from the major cities has become the norm. Poor quality of urban amenities and housing crisis go hand in hand in the newer urban areas. Primacy of Dhaka and Chittagong has led to over-congestion and consequently a breakdown in transportation systems. Development of surface road network is given a much higher priority than water transport and railway systems. The pattern and extent of urbanization could be shaped if policies would base a regional system with a transportation network using surface transport, railroads and water transport.

The quality of life in the urban areas is much lower as described by the quantitative indicators. The less tangible but probably more important issue is the loss of social cohesion (Islam, 2012).

7 Policymaking, urbanization and sustainable development in developing nations

Defined in the Brundtland Report titled, "Our Common Future" as "development which meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs", sustainable development has become the key objective across the globe with varying measures of success (UN, 1987, UN, 2008).

Elliott (2012) states that widely acceptable definitions of sustainable development are:

'In principle, such an optimal (sustainable growth) policy would seek to maintain an "acceptable" rate of growth in per-capita real incomes without depleting the national capital asset stock or the natural environmental asset stock.' (Turner, 1988)

'The net productivity of biomass (positive mass balance per unit area per unit time) maintained over decades to centuries.' (Conway, 1987)

'Development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.' (Development, 1987)

Most definitions of sustainable development encompass the idea that there are three interdependent pillars of sustainable development: environmental, economic and social. Barbier (1987) presented these as three interlocking circles as seen in Figure 7.

Figure 7: The objectives of sustainable development.

Source: Compiled from Barbier (Elliott, 2012)

Critical objectives and necessary conditions for sustainable development as identified by the World Commission on Environment and Development (Development, 1987):

- Reviving growth
- Changing the quality of growth
- Meeting essential needs for jobs, food, energy, water and sanitation
- Ensuring a sustainable level of population
- Conserving and enhancing the resource base
- Re orientating technology and managing risk
- Merging environment and economics in decision-making
- Pursuit of sustainable development requires:
 - A political system that secures effective citizen participation in decision-making
 - An economic system that provides solutions for the tensions arising from disharmonious development
 - A production system that respects the obligation to preserve the ecological base for development
 - A technological system that fosters sustainable patterns of trade and finance

- An international system that fosters sustainable patterns of trade and finance
- An administrative system that is flexible and has the capacity for self-correction

As in most developing countries, 'The reigning orientation of development is purely economic growth', which puts the environment in danger.

Bangladesh is not above the general institutional setbacks which the Brundtland Report further elaborates on the challenges of ensuring sustainability. Generally Institutions and agencies responsible for managing economic development are not open to the integrated approaches required to ensure sustainability. It states that to ensure sustainability government must take a much broader view of urban policy, recognize explicit spatial biases of economic policy and must go beyond physical and spatial planning than has been traditional.

8. The Sustainable Development Strategy, GoB 2010-21

The General Economics Division, Planning Commission of the Government has prepared the National Sustainable Development Strategy 2010-21 (NSDS) to address sustainable development of the nation. It duly emphasizes the need to take measures ensuring high economic growth rate to reduce unemployment and poverty. It is cognizant of the fact that "achieving high growth is so urgent that it is easy to downplay the right of the next generation to natural resources. But a large and growing population living in a relatively small geographical area which is increasingly pressurizing our environment – air, water and soil, dictates the urgency of sustainable development in the country." Given that, the document falls short of providing policy guidance to ensure a proper coordination between sectoral and spatial policy, the crucial ingredient to ensure convergence of various agencies involved. Existing administrative and policy framework is deemed enough barring some emphasis on improving urban housing and urban amenities.

9 Applying contemporary spatial planning practices for sustainable development in Bangladesh

9.1 The search for appropriate planning strategies and techniques for Bangladesh:

As seen from the preceding chapters, it is evident that Bangladesh faces challenges to gain sustainable

development that are quite unprecedented from a spatial point of view, a few of them are extremely high population density, unplanned urbanization, dependence on agriculture and hydro-ecological threats.

Master Planning, land-use planning, environment planning, urban planning, project planning, sectoral planning, regional planning, transportation planning etc. were and still are among the tools used by planners to strike a balance between present and future needs and resources. Such efforts often ended in the form of essentially top down, 'fixed' blueprints/masterplans/strategies which did not work simply because of the unpredictable character of development in the developing world and lack of coordination between implementing agencies.

Since the post second world war era, the role of urban and regional planners have evolved from the 'designer town planner' to the more 'rational/scientific process analyst manager/ strategist' who are open to the demands of a dynamic world and becoming more and more interconnected, urbanized as well as cognizant of the environmental issues (Taylor, 1999, Friedmann, 2005). Planning culture, strategies and mechanisms and tools vary greatly across the globe with response to local socio-political exigencies of nation states.

Any planning effort which takes the demography, economics, environment and nature of governance into cognizance with sustainability as a performance criteria must ensure integration with the policies and actions of the key agencies, participatory methods, flexibility and adaptability. Such efforts initiate the necessity of new institutional frameworks (UN, 1987, Davidson, 1996). Conflicts arise when one type of plan aims to provide the performance required in all areas. Some sensitive areas require statutory measures for control, whereas others may require a flexible framework to adapt for in order to change conditions (Davidson, 1996). In such a demanding context, spatial planning aims to address the complex issues faced by planners in the contemporary world (Cullingworth and Nadin, 2006). In 1983, the Council of Europe declared The European regional/Spatial Planning Charter, also known as the Torremolinos Charter, which defines spatial planning: "Regional/spatial planning gives geographical expression to the economic, social, cultural and ecological policies of society" (Europe, 1983). It is at the same time a scientific discipline, an administrative technique and a policy developed as an interdisciplinary and comprehensive approach directed towards a balanced regional development and the physical organization of space according to an overall strategy."

Spatial planning is a multi-sectoral public sector activity at all levels, encompassing activity from planning, monitoring, analysis, implementation with the

necessary flexibility to adopt statutory, action and strategic planning techniques as deemed appropriate. The new context of spatial development occurring in the developing countries demands a reappraisal of both planning techniques and legislation. Short term action plans may be combined with long term visions. Government agencies with rigidly defined departments (UN, 2008).

Faludi (2000) describes the nature of the Dutch planning system, which applies the principles of spatial planning at local, municipal, provincial and national levels both for strategic and project planning. A dynamic process is initiated from the continuous evaluation of the combination of both indicative spatial planning and strategic planning. A pragmatic, well-coordinated, action oriented system ensures a continuous process among the agencies. Faludi also characterized the application of spatial planning techniques at two broad levels, project plans and strategic plans. He also suggests a form of rigorous evaluation criteria based on the planning doctrine which “requires a form of macro-analysis whereby the interaction between plans and the decisions and actions shaping the environment are put in a wider context. Between them the micro-analysis of the performance of strategic, indicative plans and the macro-analysis of these broader patterns can give a better understanding of how spatial planning performs in our society.”

9.2 Application of spatial planning for Bangladesh

Application of contemporary spatial planning practices on a national scale for Bangladesh has the potential to coordinate the activities of seemingly disparate sectors such as industry, agriculture and service to ensure sustainable development. Unsustainable development feeds environmental destruction and social injustice and in turn social unrest. The present and future needs of the tremendous density of population can be addressed if sectoral planning are combined with spatial planning. Planners must respond to the unique issues of Bangladesh and formulate planning systems with adequate machinery to respond to this unique task.

The key goals may be as follows:

- i. Creating a spatial planning authority with necessary statutory powers and capacity to consolidate all sectoral planning activities with spatial implications by various agencies. This authority which will work both centrally and at the local government level spanning its activities from the rural areas to the urban settlements.
- ii. Formulating a national policy framework to combine water resources, river basin management with land use planning and agricultural zoning.
- iii. Establishing a guideline for land-use considering the carrying capacity of water resources and suitability for farming based on productivity of eco-agriculture zones.
- iv. Consolidation of non-farming land use to such as industry, commerce, housing by using appropriate zoning codes and density indices with an intention to develop networks of small, medium and large cities integrated with both riverine and, railroads and surface transportation systems. Such urban zones can be established on lands with low agricultural productivity.
- v. Devising policies and spatial planning techniques for special areas such as coastal zones, ecologically critical areas, flood and disaster prone areas etc. to ensure resilience and adaption to climate change.

10 Conclusion

The demographic, economic and environmental trends of Bangladesh demands a holistic approach to address the gap between sectoral policy and spatial policy. Since the 1980's the quest for sustainable development has initiated a paradigm shift in policy making across the globe. So far spatial planning has not been given due emphasis by the policymakers of Bangladesh. The adverse impact of the present demographic, urbanization and economic trends on the environment and quality of life will become detrimental to the hard won path to progress if the policymakers fail to take spatial planning as an essential component of governance.

The demographic, economic and environmental context will require a framework of spatial planning tailored specifically for Bangladesh. Such a framework must be responsive to the specific exigencies of the demographic, economic, environmental, social and political context of Bangladesh. This paper does not aim to delineate a spatial planning system for Bangladesh. It recommends that comprehensive spatial planning is necessary for sustainable development of Bangladesh.

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